

Preparedness and Resilience Enforcement for Critical Infrastructure Cascading Cyberphysical Threats (PRECINCT)

Press Release: PRECINCT Living Lab 3 Operations - Athens

PRECINCT aims to connect private and public CI (Critical Infrastructure) stakeholders in a geographical area under a common cyber-physical security management approach which will yield a protected territory for citizens and infrastructures. PRECINCT consortium consists of CIs representing the transport, water, energy and ICT sectors as well as law enforcement agencies who are actively involved in shaping the project development and outputs. Furthermore, PRECINCT project also includes 4 Living Labs that will be set up and test the developed concepts as well as these will be further validated in 3 Demonstrators in the EU.

PRECINCT Living Lab 3 Athens Operations – Kick Off

PRECINCT Living Lab 3 (LL3) – Athens kicked off in September 2022 and will last 9 months in total, until the 30th September 2023 (end of the project). PRECINCT LL3 – Athens consists of three CIs providing transport services to thousands of citizens daily in the same broader geographical area of Athens, highlighting the importance and needs for resilience management of interconnected transport CIs. More specifically, those are:

- ❖ **Athens International Airport (AIA)** the largest and busiest international airport in Greece, serving the city of Athens region.
- ❖ **Atiikes Diadromes S.A.** responsible for the operation and maintenance of the **Attiki Odos Motorway**. The motorway mainly links the airport to the city center, as well as other public transport modes.
- ❖ **AMETPO** owner of infrastructure and critical assets of the Athens Metro. Attiko Metro is the owner of Critical Infrastructure assets (tunnels, stations, depots, etc.) of the Athens Metro network.

During PRECINCT Living Lab 3 Operations the goal is to develop various cyber-physical attack scenarios and test the PRECINCT Platform in terms of facilitating the communications and coordination among the various stakeholders in critical situation as well as increasing the resilience along the Athens urban Transportation network.

PRECINCT Living Lab 3 – Operations and Crisis Management Discussions

As part of PRECINCT LL3 Operations, a series of visits to LL3 Operations and Crisis Management centers took place. The goals of these visits were to:

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- Raise awareness among stakeholders about PRECINCT project and Living Lab results
- Provide an overview of daily operations and critical assets/infrastructure of LL3 CIs
- Discuss Crisis Management Procedures and Incident Detection

In more detail, the first workshop took place on the 19th of January at the Athens International Airport (AIA) and Attikes Diadromes' headquarters. The discussions started with an overview of the PRECINCT H2020 project and the LL3 objectives, followed by the presentation of AIA Crisis Management procedures, a round-table discussion about CIs interdependencies and on-site demonstration of AIA critical services. The visit concluded with a visit to the Attiki Odos Traffic Management center and presentations regarding incident management processes.

The second visit took place on the 31st of January at STASY Operation Control Center by STASY. In this workshop Attiko Metro representatives elaborated on the Athens metro infrastructure per activity power supply, train operation, public information systems etc. as well as STASY representatives provided an overview of the Metro line 2 and 3 Control Center day-to-day operations and incidents affecting the normal operation.

Finally, the third workshop was carried out online and included the demonstration of KEMEA's Hellenic Coordination Center for Critical Infrastructure Protection (H3CIP). H3CIP will be demonstrated in the Athens Region Transport Resilience Living Lab with the goal of providing a common operational picture in near-real time to all stakeholders connected to the H3CIP platform; supporting the exchange of information among participating AMETRO, AIA, ATTIKES DIADROMES operators during an incident; and facilitating coordination among the involved stakeholders during a crisis.

Finally, as part of the workshop agenda representatives from LL3 CIs had an opportunity to meet Crisis Management representatives from the other organizations, share knowledge and best practices from past events, and discuss potential synergies and collaborations for achieving effective and timely communication with involved stakeholders.

For more information, please contact: <https://www.precinct.info/en/contact/>

